

Another reference to the speed of light by the Great Pyramid

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Abstract

There are several known connections between the Great Pyramid and the speed of light. This paper shows a new method, utilising the three most famous irrational numbers, π , φ , and e , which are all embedded in the Great Pyramid's dimensions, as well as elsewhere at Giza. This neatly expresses an excellent approximation of c using Khufu's base and π , φ , and e .

Keywords: History of Mathematics, History of Science, π , φ , e .

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1 Introduction

One of the more puzzling aspects about Giza in general, and the Great Pyramid in particular, are the connections to the speed of light. There are various ways to show the connection, discussed below, which correlate quite closely to the speed of light as we have measured it. Whether this is by design, or co-incidence, depends on the viewer. I show a new method, which is mathematically similar to the well-known difference between Khufu's circumcircle and incircle. The method is conceptually completely different, more algebraic than geometric, and produces a more accurate result.

2 Symbols and values

Table 1 shows the usual irrationals. Construction is a practical art, so we need to use practical values for certain irrationals. It appears that while they used 3.1416 as π when needed, they were happy to approximate

that to simpler versions like 3.14 or 3.142 when showing intent rather than exactitude was sufficient. Even today, we still use 22/7 or 3.14 in school.

Symbol	Name	“Full” value	Practical value	Practical % Accuracy
π	Archimedes’ constant	3.141592653...	3.1416 or 3.142 or 3.14	99.9998, 99.9870 or 99.9493
e	Euler’s number	2.718281828...	2.7183 or 2.718 or 2.72	99.9993 or 99.9896 or 99.9368
φ	Golden ratio	1.6180339887...	1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979
$\sqrt{2}$	Root 2	1.414213562...	1.4142	99.9990
€	Royal cubit	0.5236 m	$\pi/6$ rounded	

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

Equations shown below sometimes use a science/engineering approach, not pure mathematics, so 1.999 = 2.0.

We are dealing with a different culture, which may have had a different approach to accuracy and precision, compared to our modern scientific mindset. My Giza analysis suggests they typically worked to 3 or 4 decimal places. This may indicate that they used abacuses or counting tables, or possibly slide rules or logarithms, to calculate. Alternatively, they may just have used four decimals as anything more did not make sense in construction. 0.0001 € is 0.05236 mm, which is about 50 microns, half the smallest distance that can be seen with the naked eye, and approaching the length of a human liver cell.

I use “cubit” for the Royal cubit (€). Other researchers use other values, but 0.5236 works for me.

3 The speed of light in metres and cubits per second

The speed of light is currently determined to be 299 792 458 m/s. For the purposes of this discussion, we can also write that as 299.792458 Mm/s or 29.9792458 x 10⁷ m/s.

We can convert to cubits by dividing by either 0.5236, or $\frac{\pi}{6}$, as shown in table 2.

Conversion	€/s	M€/s
0.5236	572 560 080.2	572.5600802
$\pi/6$	572 561 419.1	572.5614191

Table 2: Speed of light in €/s and M€/s

4 Khufu and the speed of light

I know of five claims regarding Khufu’s pyramid and the speed of light. These are the latitude, the difference between the circumcircle and the incircle, and approximations from passage and other lengths. I shall cover these briefly.

The latitude of the centre, as measured currently by satellite, and using the latest model of the Earth, as conveniently tracked by Wikipedia’s network [1], is 29° 58’ 45” N, or 29.979167° N in decimal degrees.

This latitude of 29.979167° closely matches the speed of light at 29.9792458 x 10⁷ m/s shown above. In m/s, the difference would be 299 792 458 – 299 791 670 = 788 m/s.

The problem with this approach is that the “measured latitude” has varied over time. It depends on the World Geodetic System [2] model, which has changed over time [3]. Also, while the current latitude is a good match now, it was not necessarily so at construction once you factor in continental drift (*Nubian Plate, North West Region* [4]) since Giza was built, which is at least 4500 years ago, and possibly much longer (*Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* [5]).

Scott Onstott credits this discovery to Webb [6]. An article from 2013 [7] claimed the line went through the Grand Gallery, so possibly the GPS model was re-aligned between then and now.

Another reference is Spivey’s *The Great Pyramid’s conspicuous speed of light latitude is no accident* [8].

The second claim revolves around the difference between Khufu’s circumcircle and incircle, as shown in Figure 1, which shows the top view outline of the great pyramid with a side of 440 \mathbb{G} .

The red contained incircle has a diameter of 440 \mathbb{G} , while the blue surrounding circumcircle has a diameter of $440\sqrt{2}$ \mathbb{G} .

Figure 1: The circumcircle and incircle for Khufu

The circumference of the incircle is $\pi d = 440\pi$.

The circumference of the circumcircle is $\pi D = 440\sqrt{2}\pi$.

The difference between them is

$$440\sqrt{2}\pi - 440\pi = 440\pi(\sqrt{2} - 1)$$

The question is, what are the values for π and $\sqrt{2}$?

We either use “full” values, in practice about 9 decimals, although modern calculators may work to 17 places internally, or a more pragmatic approach as in Table 1, using 3.1416 for π and 1.4142 for $\sqrt{2}$.

Using full values, the difference is 572.5677252 \mathbb{G} , while using rounded values, the difference is 572.5503168 \mathbb{G} . These values are close. We can compare them to the speed of light as shown in Table 3.

	Full values	Rounded values
c in $M\mathbb{G}$	572.5614191	572.5600802
Circles difference \mathbb{G}	572.5677252	572.5503168
Difference to c	0.006306110	0.009763400
Scaled ($\times 10^6$)	6306.110	9763.400
Convert to m/s	3301.872	5112.116

Table 3: Circles differences

The earliest source I can find attributes this method to Jonathan Langdale [7].

I covered this method in more detail in *G1, c and G: Khufu’s pyramid, the speed of light, and the royal cubit, compared* [9]).

The next three methods are based on measurements of specific distances in Khufu.

In *The King’s Chamber Floor, decoded* [10], I showed how the floor blocks represented the usual favourite numbers, like π , φ , e , α , and assorted square roots. There were also two references to the square of the speed of light. First, a length in \mathbb{G} that is numerically c^2 in metres, to a suitable power of ten of course. This is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Metre speed of light squared shown in cubits

Figure 3 shown the same idea, except this time the distance is in metres. The King’s Chamber is 20 Ɔ long.

Figure 3: Metre speed of light squared shown in metres

It is curious that the references are to c^2 rather than c .

Both of these are based on measurements by Smyth (*Life and work at the Great Pyramid*[11]), and depend entirely on Smyth’s accuracy, which may be suspect.

The last link between Khufu and the speed of light is shown by Larry Pahl in *Speed of Light in the Great Pyramid Passages and Chambers* [12]. Pahl’s novel approach adds various distances, using historical as well as his own measurements, to build the speed of light, a digit or two at a time. Each section measured was rounded to the nearest metre.

5 A new method using Thoth’s Constant

The Great Pyramid’s design, with a base of 440 Ɔ, half base of 220 Ɔ, and height of 280 Ɔ, provides approximations for π , φ , and e , as follows:

$$\frac{\text{twice base}}{\text{height}} = \frac{2 \times 440}{280} = 3.142857 \approx \pi$$

The side slope is $\sqrt{220^2 + 280^2} = 356.089876$.

Then $\frac{\text{side slope}}{\text{half base}} = \frac{356.089876}{220} = 1.61859 \approx \varphi$, and

$$\frac{\text{base area}}{100 \times \text{twice side slope}} = \frac{440^2}{100 \times 2 \times 356.089876} = 2.7184 \approx e$$

Here, the 100 is a scaling factor. Instead of squaring the base, you could multiply the base by half the base, and dividing that by the side slope will give you approximately $100e$.

These are reasonable approximations, given that irrationals can not be written as simple fractions exactly, and three components (440, 220 and 280) are integers.

Critics like to point out that “3.142857 is not π ”. That is true, and disingenuous in at least two ways. Firstly, schools all over the world use that number, in the form of $\frac{22}{7}$, when teaching children about π . If it is good enough for the global education system, why is it not good enough for Giza?

Secondly, π is irrational and can not be written exactly as a fraction. All we can do is approximate it to varying degrees of accuracy. Critics should instead suggest which integer dimensions for a pyramid the size and shape of Khufu would satisfy them better.

This objection also misses the point that Khufu approximates not only π , but φ and e as well. Alan Green (*Great Pyramid's Astounding Math Constants* [13]) points out several other numbers that can be derived from Khufu's dimensions.

We can turn the problem around and ask what dimensions would give better approximations. We keep the base fixed at 440 \mathbb{G} , because the base has to be 440 for other reasons than the speed of light calculation shown earlier, and vary the height. That gives us:

For π , the height needs to be 280.1126998 \mathbb{G} . That is 5.9 cm more than 280 \mathbb{G} .

For φ , the height needs to be 279.8443229 \mathbb{G} . That is 8.15 cm less than 280 \mathbb{G} .

For e , the height needs to be 280.0221571 \mathbb{G} . That is 1.16 cm more than 280 \mathbb{G} .

To do all three at once, we take the average, which is $\frac{280.1126998+279.8443229+280.0221571}{3} = 279.9930599$. That differs from 280 \mathbb{G} by 0.006940082 \mathbb{G} , which is 3.6338 mm, on a structure 146.6 m tall.

Thoth's constant (discussed below) combines these most famous irrationals π , φ and e , into one number.

* * *

The method shown in §4 with the circles, can be conceptually described as “circumcircle minus incircle”. When reduced to a formula, shown above as

$$c \approx 440\pi(\sqrt{2} - 1)$$

it is essentially nothing more than

$$c \approx \text{base} \times \text{constant}$$

where the constant is $\pi(\sqrt{2} - 1)$.

The new method uses exactly this approach, with *Thoth's Constant* [14], symbol ϑ .

Thoth's Constant is defined as

$$\vartheta = \frac{\pi\varphi}{e}$$

Wolfram Alpha (https://www.wolframalpha.com/input?i=pi*phi/e) computes that as

1.87000613368955001896323177216265845824996304372...

which rounds very nicely to a practical value of 1.87.

A culture without access to digital computers may instead have calculated it as

$$\vartheta = \frac{3.1416 \times 1.618}{2.7183} = 1.8699587242...$$

or, using 3 digits,

$$\vartheta = \frac{3.142 \times 1.618}{2.718} = 1.87040323767476...$$

Both of these results still round to 1.87.

Please see my paper [14] for examples of where ϑ is used at Giza.

The designers of Giza were enamoured with φ , as evidenced by their use of the double square in several places, and basing Khufu on a Kepler Triangle design.

To approximate c , we use the three decimals version of ϑ , and take the logarithm to base 1.618, the matching version of the golden ratio φ . We multiply this by the 440 \mathcal{G} base length.

$$c \approx \text{base} \times \text{constant} \quad (1)$$

$$\approx 440 \times \log_{\varphi} \vartheta \quad (2)$$

$$\approx 440 \times \log_{1.618} 1.87040323767476 \quad (3)$$

$$\approx 440 \times 1.301259331 \quad (4)$$

$$\approx 572.5541056 \quad (5)$$

Converting back to metres using 0.5236, we have 299.7893297 Mm/s or 299 789 329.7 m/s, giving a difference to c of 3128.287 m/s.

As an aside, $\log_{10} 20$ is 1.301029996, which is close to this constant. Then $440 \log_{10} 20 = 572.4561981$, which translates to 299 736 494.5 m/s.

6 Comparing the methods

I am excluding the measurement-based methods here, since the methodologies are too different. Also, Pahl's method builds the speed of light exactly down to the last digit, so it is not comparable to the other approaches.

Method	Value	Difference	Comments
c	299 792 458.0		
Latitude	299 791 670.0	788.000	Depends on Globe model, continental drift
Circles full values	299 795 759.8	3301.872	
Circles rounded values	299 787 346.0	5112.116	
$\log_{10} 20$	299 736 494.5	55 963.479	
$\log_{1.618} \vartheta$	299 789 329.7	3128.287	

Table 4: Comparison of the results

7 Critique

The key steps in the above method are calculating the particular version of ϑ using 3 decimals, then keeping all the decimals in the result, and taking the log to base 1.618, again keeping all the decimals. This could be construed as cherry-picking, as well as raising questions about how to calculate logs to base 1.618. It's easy with modern calculators, but rather more tedious by hand.

I'm not going to discuss questions about decimal notation, the place-value system, etc. The dynastic Egyptians did not use them, but it is clear to me from my research that whoever built Giza, did. See for example *The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game* [15] where assorted important numbers are spelled out in decimal notation.

The speed of light is difficult to measure. Figure 4 shows the final results from Essen and Gordon-Smith [16], showing that their value is an average from different tests, after picking the best set-up. These are also in km/s, not m/s.

date	mode of resonance	correction factor ($1 + 1/2Q$)	constant r	measured frequency f'_{imn} (Mcyc./sec.)	v_0 (km./sec.)
2. x. 46	E_{010}	1.000028	2.404825	3101.25	299,793
2. x. 46	E_{011}	1.000035	2.404825	3563.80	299,791
25. x. 46	E_{010}	1.000028	2.404825	3101.28	299,796
25. x. 46	E_{011}	1.000035	2.404825	3563.77	299,789
mean value of velocity 299,792 km./sec.					

Figure 4: Essen and Gordon-Smith final results

We also have no idea, if Khufu was indeed intended to provide a reference to c in addition to other requirements in the site plan, what the target value was. Wikipedia [17] conveniently lists some historical values,

as in Table 5. I’ve added Giza, calculated from the maximum and minimum of the circles method, and corrected some figures [18].

Year	Who, method	Value km/s	% Accuracy
2750 BCE / 55.5k BCE	Giza (official date / my date)	299 791.553 ± 4.207	99.999698
1675	Rømer and Huygens, moons of Jupiter	220 000	73.384101
1729	James Bradley, aberration of light	301 000	99.597207
1849	Hippolyte Fizeau, toothed wheel	315 000	94.927310
1862	Léon Foucault, rotating mirror	298 000 ± 500	99.402100
1907	Rosa and Dorsey, EM constants	299 788 ± 30	99.998513
1926	Albert A. Michelson, rotating mirror	299 796 ± 4	99.998819
1950	Essen and Gordon-Smith, cavity resonator	299 792	99.999847
1958	K.D. Froome, radio interferometry	299 792.50 ± 0.10	99.999986
1972	Evenson et al., laser interferometry	299 792.457 ± 0.0011	99.999999
1983	17th CGPM, definition of the metre	299 792.458 (as defined)	100.000000

Table 5: Historical values for c

8 Conclusion

The formula, $c \approx 440 \log_{\varphi} \vartheta$, neatly combines Khufu’s base, π , φ , and e and links them to a universal constant, the speed of light.

From Table 4, we see that the method using a selected version of Thoth’s Constant provides a better result than the well-known “circumcircle minus incircle” method.

The latitude method gives the overall best approximation currently, but that will change as time goes by.

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